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Research Article

COMPUTATIONAL ANALYSIS OF PIPER LONGUM BIOACTIVE COMPOUNDS TARGETING COVID 19 VIRUS M PRO

Prabha.B, Shamlin E. Ashwini, Jeyasheely.J.

Bethlahem College of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Karungal, Kanyakumari District,
Tamil Nadu, India.

Abstract:

Background: The COVID-19 pandemic, caused by SARS-CoV-2, has posed a significant global health threat. Despite advances in medicine, effective treatments remain limited. The COVID-19 main protease (Mpro) is a crucial enzyme for viral replication, making it an attractive target for drug development. Piper longum, a traditional medicinal plant, has shown antiviral and therapeutic properties, making it a potential candidate for COVID-19 treatment. This study explores the potential of piper longum bioactive compounds as COVID-19 Mpro inhibitors through molecular docking.

Material and Methods: Ten phytochemical constituents of Piper longum were selected and docked against COVID-19 Mpro (PDB ID: 6LU7) using molecular docking tools. The protein structure was obtained from the Protein Data Bank, and ligand structures were retrieved from PubChem.

Results: All selected ligands showed good binding energy towards COVID-19 Mpro, ranging from -5.59 kcal/mol to -9.56 kcal/mol. Piperundecalidine exhibited the highest binding affinity (-9.56 kcal/mol), indicating its potential as a COVID-19 Mpro inhibitor. The study highlights the potential of Piper longum bioactive compounds as COVID-19 Mpro inhibitors, with Piperundecalidine showing promising results. The findings suggest that Piper longum, a traditionally used medicinal plant, could be a potential herbal remedy against COVID-19.

Conclusion: The study identifies Piper longum bioactive compounds, particularly Piperundecalidine, as potential COVID-19 Mpro inhibitors, warranting further in vitro and in vivo evaluations to repurpose the fruit of Piper longum against COVID-19.

KEYWORDS: COVID-19, Piper longum, Protein, Ligand, Molecular docking

Corresponding author:

Shamlin E. Ashwini,
Bethlahem College of Pharmaceutical Sciences,
Karungal, Kanyakumari District,
Tamil Nadu, India.

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INTRODUCTION:

The COVID-19 is an extremely contagious and pathogenic viral infection caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), which emerged in Wuhan, China and spread throughout the world. Genomic analysis revealed that SARS-CoV-2 is phylogenetically related to SARS-like (severe acute respiratory syndrome like bat viruses) therefore bats could be the possible primary reservoir. There is no clinically approved antiviral drug or vaccine available to be used against COVID-19. However, few broad- spectrum antiviral drugs have been evaluated against COVID-19 in clinical trials, resulted in clinical recovery. On February 6, 2020, worldwide protein data bank has established COVID-19 coronavirus resources to facilitate target-based drug design efforts against current global threat. Latter COVID-19 virus main protease (PDB ID: 6LU7) was found as key CoV enzyme, which plays a pivotal role in mediating viral replication and transcription, making it an attractive drug target for this virus.² Earthen hemisphere is gifted with varieties of large number of medicinal herbs. Herbal drugs have become popular remedies, due to the lower risk of adverse effects⁵.

Among them, Piper longum is important medicinal plant used in various systems of Indian medicine especially in Siddha and Ayurvedic system of medicine. This plant is inexpensive, readily available, and effective for many diseases, including cancer, inflammation, depression, diabetes, obesity, and hepatotoxicity. This study aims to identify the bioactive compounds of Piper Longum as potential COVID-19 Mpro inhibitors (PDB ID: 6LU7) through molecular docking. It is key tool which is used extensively in computer-assisted drug design. The goal of ligand-protein docking is to predict the predominant binding model and possible interactions of a ligand with a known three-dimensional structure of protein.¹

MATERIALS AND METHODS:**MATERIALS****Soft wares**

ACD labs ChemSketch
Molinspiration
PASS online
AmDock
SwissADME

PROTEIN DATA BANK

The protein data bank is a database for the three-dimensional structural data of large biological molecule such as proteins and nucleic acids. The data, typically obtained by x ray crystallography, NMR spectroscopy or increasingly, cryo-electron microscopy. The data is freely accessible on the internet via the websites of its member organizations (PDBe, PDBJ, RCSB and BMRB). Data is submitted by Biologists and Biochemists from all around the world to be freely accessible on internet via its member organizations websites and is updated weekly. The protein for molecular docking can be downloaded from this website. Usually proteins having highest resolution (1.0-2.0) is preferred for docking.⁹

PROTEINS/ MAC

COVID-19 Mpro (PDB ID: 6LU7) structures were obtained from PDB (<https://www.rcsb.org/>) in pdb format. PDB is an archive for the crystal structures of biological macromolecules, worldwide. The Mpro protein contains two chains, A and B, which form a homodimer. Chain A was used for macromolecule preparation.⁷

Fig No 1 : Fruit of piper longum

COVID-19 Mpro

Fig No:2 COVID-19 Mpro

SELECTION OF LIGANDS

The fruit of *P. longum* (Figure.1) contains a large number of alkaloids and related compounds.¹¹ Among them, ten reported phytochemical constituents were selected as ligands. The 3D structures of the selected ligands were obtained from the <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/> website in the SDF format.

METHODS

Selected Compounds with ACD ChemSketch Data

Structure and SMILES notation of quinoxaline derivatives carried out using ChemSketch was discussed in the given below⁶

COMPOUNDS	STRUCTURE	SMILES
P1	<p style="text-align: center;">Asarinin</p>	<chem>C1C2C(COC2C3=CC4=C(C=C3)OCO4)C(O1)C5=CC6=C(C=C5)OCO6</chem>
P2	<p style="text-align: center;">Pellitorine</p>	<chem>CCCCC=CC=CC(=O)NCC(C)C</chem>
P3	<p style="text-align: center;">Piperanine</p>	<chem>C1CCN(CC1)C(=O)/C=C/CCC2=CC3=C(C=C2)OCO3</chem>
P4	<p style="text-align: center;">Piperine</p>	<chem>C1CCN(CC1)C(=O)C=CC=CC2=CC3=C(C=C2)OCO3</chem>
P5	<p style="text-align: center;">Piperlongumine</p>	<chem>COC1=CC(=CC(=C1OC)OC)/C=C/C(=O)N2C(C=C2)=O</chem>

<p>P6</p>	<p>Piperlongumine</p>	<chem>CC(C)CNC(=O)/C=C/C=C/C1=CC2=C(C=C1)OCO2</chem>
<p>P7</p>	<p>Piperolein B</p>	<chem>C1CCN(CC1)C(=O)CCCCC/C=C/C2=CC3=C(C=C2)OC3</chem>
<p>P8</p>	<p>Piperundecalidine</p>	<chem>C1CCN(CC1)C(=O)/C=C/C=C/CCCC/C=C/C2=CC3=C(C=C2)OC3</chem>
<p>P9</p>	<p>Pipericide</p>	<chem>CC(C)CNC(=O)/C=C/C=C/CCCC/C=C/C1=CC2=C(C=C1)OCO2</chem>
<p>P10</p>	<p>Piperettine</p>	<chem>C1CCN(CC1)C(=O)/C=C/C=C/C=C/C2=CC3=C(C=C2)OC3</chem>

Data obtained from Molinspiration Software

The Lipinski Rule of 5 is calculated and analyzed results are shown below

COMPOUNDS	MOLINSPIRATIONRESULTS																		
P1	<p>molinspiration</p> <p>originalSMILES <chem>C1C2C(COC2C3=CC4=C(C=C3)OCO4)C(O1)C5=CC6=C(C=C5)OCO6</chem> miSMILES: <chem>C1C2C(COC2C3=CC4=C(C=C3)OCO4)C(O1)C5=CC6=C(C=C5)OCO6</chem> Asarinin</p> <p>Molinspiration property engine v2022.08</p> <table border="0"> <tr><td>miLogP</td><td>3.69</td></tr> <tr><td>TPSA</td><td>55.40</td></tr> <tr><td>natoms</td><td>26</td></tr> <tr><td>MW</td><td>354.36</td></tr> <tr><td>nON</td><td>6</td></tr> <tr><td>nOHNH</td><td>0</td></tr> <tr><td>nviolations</td><td>0</td></tr> <tr><td>nrotb</td><td>2</td></tr> <tr><td>volume</td><td>300.51</td></tr> </table> <p>Get data as text (for copy / paste). Get 3D geometry BETA</p>	miLogP	3.69	TPSA	55.40	natoms	26	MW	354.36	nON	6	nOHNH	0	nviolations	0	nrotb	2	volume	300.51
miLogP	3.69																		
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nrotb	2																		
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P2	<p>molinspiration</p> <p>originalSMILES <chem>CCCCC=CC=CC(=O)NCC(C)C</chem> miSMILES: <chem>CCCCC=CC=CC(=O)NCC(C)C</chem> Pellitorin</p> <p>Molinspiration property engine v2022.08</p> <table border="0"> <tr><td>miLogP</td><td>4.26</td></tr> <tr><td>TPSA</td><td>29.10</td></tr> <tr><td>natoms</td><td>16</td></tr> <tr><td>MW</td><td>223.36</td></tr> <tr><td>nON</td><td>2</td></tr> <tr><td>nOHNH</td><td>1</td></tr> <tr><td>nviolations</td><td>0</td></tr> <tr><td>nrotb</td><td>8</td></tr> <tr><td>volume</td><td>249.37</td></tr> </table> <p>Get data as text (for copy / paste). Get 3D geometry BETA</p>	miLogP	4.26	TPSA	29.10	natoms	16	MW	223.36	nON	2	nOHNH	1	nviolations	0	nrotb	8	volume	249.37
miLogP	4.26																		
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nOHNH	1																		
nviolations	0																		
nrotb	8																		
volume	249.37																		

<p>P3</p>	<p>molinspiration</p> <p>originalSMILES <chem>C1CCN(CC1)C(=O)C=CCCC2=CC3=C(C=C2)OCO3</chem> miSMILES: <chem>C1CCN(CC1)C(=O)C=CCCC2=CC3=C(C=C2)OCO3</chem> 5-(2H-1,3-Benzodioxol-5-yl)-1-(piperidin-1-yl)pent-2-en-1-one</p> <p>molinspiration</p> <p>Molinspiration property engine v2022.08</p> <table border="0"> <tr><td>miLogP</td><td>3.30</td></tr> <tr><td>TPSA</td><td>38.78</td></tr> <tr><td>natoms</td><td>21</td></tr> <tr><td>MW</td><td>287.36</td></tr> <tr><td>nON</td><td>4</td></tr> <tr><td>nOHNH</td><td>0</td></tr> <tr><td>nviolations</td><td>0</td></tr> <tr><td>nrotb</td><td>4</td></tr> <tr><td>volume</td><td>273.93</td></tr> </table> <p>Get data as text (for copy / paste).</p> <p>Get 3D geometry BETA</p>	miLogP	3.30	TPSA	38.78	natoms	21	MW	287.36	nON	4	nOHNH	0	nviolations	0	nrotb	4	volume	273.93
miLogP	3.30																		
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<p>P4</p>	<p>molinspiration</p> <p>originalSMILES <chem>C1CCN(CC1)C(=O)/C=C/C=C/C2=CC3=C(C=C2)OCO3</chem> miSMILES: <chem>C1CCN(CC1)C(=O)/C=C/C=C/C2=CC3=C(C=C2)OCO3</chem></p> <p>molinspiration</p> <p>Molinspiration property engine v2022.08</p> <table border="0"> <tr><td>miLogP</td><td>3.33</td></tr> <tr><td>TPSA</td><td>38.78</td></tr> <tr><td>natoms</td><td>21</td></tr> <tr><td>MW</td><td>285.34</td></tr> <tr><td>nON</td><td>4</td></tr> <tr><td>nOHNH</td><td>0</td></tr> <tr><td>nviolations</td><td>0</td></tr> <tr><td>nrotb</td><td>3</td></tr> <tr><td>volume</td><td>267.74</td></tr> </table> <p>Get data as text (for copy / paste).</p> <p>Get 3D geometry BETA</p>	miLogP	3.33	TPSA	38.78	natoms	21	MW	285.34	nON	4	nOHNH	0	nviolations	0	nrotb	3	volume	267.74
miLogP	3.33																		
TPSA	38.78																		
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nviolations	0																		
nrotb	3																		
volume	267.74																		
<p>P5</p>	<p>molinspiration</p> <p>originalSMILES <chem>COC1=CC(=CC(=C1OC)OC)C=C/C(=O)N2CCC=CC2=O</chem> miSMILES: <chem>COC1=CC(=CC(=C1OC)OC)C=C/C(=O)N2CCC=CC2=O</chem></p> <p>molinspiration</p> <p>Molinspiration property engine v2022.08</p> <table border="0"> <tr><td>miLogP</td><td>1.62</td></tr> <tr><td>TPSA</td><td>65.08</td></tr> <tr><td>natoms</td><td>23</td></tr> <tr><td>MW</td><td>317.34</td></tr> <tr><td>nON</td><td>6</td></tr> <tr><td>nOHNH</td><td>0</td></tr> <tr><td>nviolations</td><td>0</td></tr> <tr><td>nrotb</td><td>5</td></tr> <tr><td>volume</td><td>289.03</td></tr> </table> <p>Get data as text (for copy / paste).</p> <p>Get 3D geometry BETA</p>	miLogP	1.62	TPSA	65.08	natoms	23	MW	317.34	nON	6	nOHNH	0	nviolations	0	nrotb	5	volume	289.03
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miLogP	3.30																		
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nOHNH	0																		
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nrotb	4																		
volume	295.16																		

RESULT OF PASS

The bioactivity score of quinoxaline derivatives obtained from PASS is given below

COMPOUNDS	RESULTS		
P1	Pa	Pi	Activity
	0,931	0,005	Membrane integrity agonist
	0,837	0,003	Neurotransmitter uptake inhibitor
	0,800	0,005	Caspase 3 stimulant
	0,787	0,013	Antineoplastic
	0,761	0,004	Carminative
	0,742	0,010	Antidyskinetic
	0,738	0,030	Antineurotic
	0,674	0,009	Leukopoiesis stimulant
	0,668	0,007	Antineoplastic (lung cancer)
0,689	0,028	TP53 expression enhancer	

P2	Pa	Pi	Activity
	0,875	0,008	Saccharopepsin inhibitor
	0,875	0,008	Chymosin inhibitor
	0,875	0,008	Acrocyllindropepsin inhibitor
	0,870	0,008	CYP2J substrate
	0,868	0,007	Mucomembranous protector
	0,833	0,010	Pro-opiomelanocortin converting enzyme inhibitor
	0,825	0,009	CYP2J2 substrate
	0,836	0,021	Phobic disorders treatment
	0,799	0,005	Macrophage colony stimulating factor agonist
	0,808	0,018	Polyporopepsin inhibitor
P3	Pa	Pi	Activity
	0,916	0,007	Membrane integrity agonist
	0,826	0,003	Carminative
	0,814	0,004	Neurotransmitter uptake inhibitor
	0,734	0,004	Sigma receptor agonist
	0,663	0,009	MAP kinase stimulant
	0,648	0,027	Antidyskinetic
	0,627	0,013	Ovulation inhibitor
	0,609	0,010	Antiulcerative
	0,575	0,019	Caspase 3 stimulant
	0,572	0,027	Vasodilator, peripheral
P4	Pa	Pi	Activity
	0,859	0,022	Membrane integrity agonist
	0,816	0,003	MMP9 expression inhibitor
	0,803	0,004	Neurotransmitter uptake inhibitor
	0,741	0,011	Antidyskinetic
	0,717	0,006	Carminative
	0,720	0,013	Respiratory analeptic
	0,701	0,005	Sigma receptor agonist
	0,682	0,007	Ovulation inhibitor
	0,624	0,017	Analeptic
	0,603	0,016	MAP kinase stimulant
P5	Pa	Pi	Activity
	0,900	0,011	Membrane integrity agonist
	0,818	0,003	MMP9 expression inhibitor
	0,803	0,004	Neurotransmitter uptake inhibitor
	0,775	0,004	Sigma receptor agonist
	0,774	0,004	Carminative
	0,630	0,012	Ovulation inhibitor
	0,644	0,028	Antidyskinetic
	0,628	0,018	Vasodilator, peripheral
	0,608	0,015	MAP kinase stimulant
	0,582	0,015	TNF expression inhibitor

P6	Pa	Pi	Activity
	0,752	0,046	Membrane integrity agonist
	0,692	0,013	Neurotransmitter uptake inhibitor
	0,694	0,059	Mucomembranous protector
	0,644	0,010	TNF expression inhibitor
	0,618	0,011	Carminative
	0,666	0,062	CYP2J substrate
	0,607	0,010	Antiulcerative
	0,562	0,020	MMP9 expression inhibitor
	0,533	0,040	Ovulation inhibitor
0,519	0,028	Alcohol O-acetyltransferase inhibitor	
P7	Pa	Pi	Activity
	0,762	0,008	Proteasome ATPase inhibitor
	0,689	0,015	Muramoyltetrapeptide carboxypeptidase inhibitor
	0,664	0,013	Vasodilator, peripheral
	0,641	0,018	Insulysin inhibitor
	0,641	0,025	JAK2 expression inhibitor
	0,616	0,014	MMP9 expression inhibitor
	0,654	0,054	Nootropic
	0,580	0,009	Cell adhesion molecule inhibitor
	0,590	0,030	Phosphatidylcholine-retinol O-acyltransferase inhibitor
0,564	0,010	4-Coumarate-CoA ligase inhibitor	
P8	Pa	Pi	Activity
	0,916	0,007	Membrane integrity agonist
	0,826	0,003	Carminative
	0,814	0,004	Neurotransmitter uptake inhibitor
	0,734	0,004	Sigma receptor agonist
	0,663	0,009	MAP kinase stimulant
	0,648	0,027	Antidyskinetic
	0,627	0,013	Ovulation inhibitor
	0,609	0,010	Antiulcerative
	0,575	0,019	Caspase 3 stimulant
0,572	0,027	Vasodilator, peripheral	

P9	Pa	Pi	Activity
	0,916	0,007	Membrane integrity agonist
	0,826	0,003	Carminative
	0,814	0,004	Neurotransmitter uptake inhibitor
	0,734	0,004	Sigma receptor agonist
	0,663	0,009	MAP kinase stimulant
	0,648	0,027	Antidyskinetic
	0,627	0,013	Ovulation inhibitor
	0,609	0,010	Antiulcerative
	0,575	0,019	Caspase 3 stimulant
	0,572	0,027	Vasodilator, peripheral
P10	Pa	Pi	Activity
	0,877	0,002	MMP9 expression inhibitor
	0,863	0,021	Membrane integrity agonist
	0,783	0,005	Neurotransmitter uptake inhibitor
	0,765	0,004	TNF expression inhibitor
	0,709	0,009	Vasodilator, peripheral
	0,704	0,005	Sigma receptor agonist
	0,704	0,006	Carminative
	0,693	0,005	Antiulcerative
	0,688	0,015	Respiratory analeptic
	0,651	0,013	All-trans-retinyl-palmitate hydrolase inhibitor

AM DOCK RESULTS

COMPOUNDS	DOCKED IMAGES	3-DIMAGES
P1		

MOLECULAR DOCKING RESULTS OF SELECTED LIGAND AGAINST COVID-19 PROTEASE

LIGAND NAME	BINDING ENERGY
Asrinin	-7.63
Pellitrorine	-5.59
Piperettine	-8.46

Piperine	-8.19
Piperide	-7.21
Piperanine	-7.70
Piperlongumine	-6.62
Piperlonguminine	-7.23
PiperoleinB	-7.8
Piperundecalidine	-9.56

SWISS ADME

The pharmacokinetic profile of the best docked quinoxaline derivative QUIN 8 by Swiss ADME is given below

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

All the ten selected ligands were docked against COVID-19 virus Mpro. In-silico studies revealed all the selected ligands showed good binding energy toward the target protein ranging from -5.59 kcal/mol to -9.54 kcal/mol. Except Pellitorine, all the ligand candidates shows binding energy lesser than the upper threshold (-6 kcal/mol), generally regarded as a cut-off in ligand-binding studies Especially the ligand Piperundecalidine {P8} showed higher binding affinity(- 9.54 kcal/mol).

The 3D visualization of binding of the selected ligands confirms that each of the ligands are likely to bind the same active pocket of the COVID-19 virus Mpro.

CONCLUSION:

There may be a number of molecules will show higher affinities toward COVID-19 virus Mpro. But due to the emergency situation arising in the world, it is preferred to identify an herbal remedy which is used in traditional system of medicine for a long

time. In the present study, we identified that the fruit of Piper Longum shows remarkable effect against COVID-19 virus Mpro based on molecular docking. Further in vitro and in vivo evaluations are required to repurpose the fruit of Piper Longum against 2019-CoV. The findings of the present study will provide opportunities to other researchers to identify the right drug to combat COVID-19.

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